

Effect of Land Use on Infiltration: A Survey and Perspective

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Abstract:

Infiltration is downward entry of water into the soil due to Rainfall or irrigation. It is an indicator of the soils ability to allow water movement through the soil profile. Land uses have great impact on infiltration water that in natural condition, infiltrated directly into soil. Water in the soil keeps earth alive. Soil temporally stores water, making it available plants growth and habitat for soil organism. The Study of land use effect on infiltration is required for conserve water quality, local habitat, organisms in soil and natural resources. Survey, Lab analysis, Rainfall Simulation, Infiltration models, Statistical tests (ANOVA, Co-relation, Regression etc.) are used worldwide to maintain soil and water quality and conserve biodiversity. The main contribution of this work lies in association between infiltration and various land; viz. use types which is Farmland Bamboo field, Forest Land, Tillage and Non-tillage agriculture Agricultural land, grass land native scrub forest, forest plantation, Cultivated natural and Fish Farm, Forest to agricultural Land, Oil Palm plantation, Bush fallow, continuous cultivation, Miombo woodlands; natural forest, degraded forest, intensive agriculture, abandoned agriculture, degraded regenerating forest and Albizia plantation, Agriculture Pasture, cultivated land, fallow land and woodland, Natural pasture and dry land farming. This study shall help to the society, the hydrologists, Research Scholars, Urban Planners, hydrological modeling and for rainfall runoff generation.

Keywords: Review, Land Use, Infiltration, Survey Perspective.

Introduction:

Land is habitat for plants and animals. Half of the world habitable land is used for agriculture land. The world population increased from 1 billion in 1800 to 7.7 billion today^[6]. Land do not increase it is constant but the day by day world population is increasing dramatically. Habitable land is occupied by population under various uses. Soil is the soul of land which stores water and make available for living organisms. Due to anthropogenic activities land makes impervious surface and it affects on infiltration. Selim concluded that, the natural soil had a high infiltration rate compared to the other fields due to the deep cracks in the soil and the low initial water content^[8]. Cardwell suggested that Conversion of forests to agricultural lands increases soil bulk density and decreases soil organic matter, which is an important infiltration controlling soil property also according to this study^[3]. The decreases in infiltration rates lead to losses in ground water recharge and overall water availability. Oil palm plantation (OP), bush fallow (FL) and continuous cultivation (CC) Soil Practices will sequester organic carbon, stabilize soil aggregates and improve soil water infiltration for crop production and control^[12]. Infiltration managed by mainly two forces gravity and capillary action hence study being conducted by using soil collected from various changed land use types. Renato suggested the laboratory experimental setup with adjustable soil surface gradient can be considered appropriately. It allow us to validate local infiltration model, run-

off effect and surface infiltration process. Most of the studies investigators used rainfall simulators, infiltration models, statistical tests, and lab testing^[15]. We can't see it, but most of the world's fresh water lies underground. It starts from precipitation but it seeps in ground through infiltration. Water in the ground keeps plants and animals alive. The main goal of this paper is to review the effect of various land use types on infiltration.

Table 1: Kruskal-Wallis Test on Effect of Land Use on Infiltration.

Land Use	Observations	Infiltration Rate (Median)	Average Rank	Z Score
Farmhand	34	1930	35.9	-3.61
Bamboo Field	34	2390	56.1	1.39
Forestand	32	2350	60.0	2.25
Total	100		50.5	

C.V. = 5.99147; 9.21034; 13.816; DF=2 P-Value=0.050; 0.010; 0.001 H(x)=13.32.

Table 1: Overall Infiltration rate, Slope, Intercept and R²

Soil Property	Overall Infiltration Rate	Slope	Intercept	R ²
ASSM	-0.15	0.19	-0.18	-0.02
Silt	0.05	0.11	-0.01	0.44***
Silt	-0.03	-0.06	-0.22	0.11
Clay	-0.01	-0.06	0.22*	-0.49***
SOM	0.47***	-0.17	0.40***	0.59***
Bulk Density	-0.59***	0.19	-0.40***	-0.60***
pH	-0.04	0.03	-0.27**	0.01
TC	-0.03	0.02	-0.23*	0.34***
P	0.06	0.02	0.04	0.39***
K	0.06	0.09	-0.03	0.21*
Ca	0.11	0.02	0.28**	0.12
Mg	-0.20*	0.03	-0.36***	-0.15
S	0.13	-0.11	0.20*	0.23*
Ns	-0.39***	0.17	-0.35***	-0.05
Fe	0.01	-0.05	0.17	0.29**
Mn	0.09	-0.09	0.29**	-0.18
Zn	0.19	0.01	0.11	0.38***
Cu	0.05	-0.02	-0.05	0.08
TC	0.47***	-0.17	0.40***	0.62***
TN	0.48***	-0.23*	0.33**	0.64***
CN	0.08	0.08	0.21*	0
N:SOM	0.15	-0.16	-0.01	0.35***
C:SOM	0.29**	-0.11	0.26**	0.47***

* Significant (P < 0.05) correlation between variables
 ** Significant (P < 0.01) correlation between variables
 *** Significant (P < 0.001) correlation between variables

Table 1: Average Statistic for Infiltration models

Model	Parameter	Land use			
		Agriculture	Plantations	Native scrub forest	Grasslands
Green and Ampt	r2	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.76
	Sx	91	109	105	188
Kostiakov	r2	0.79	0.84	0.96	0.87
	Sx	67	119	48	106
Horton	r2	0.8	0.96	0.85	0.82
	Sx	101	48	107	209
Philip	r2	0.83	0.87	0.86	0.78
	Sx	88	106	113	200

Table 1: Effect of land use on infiltration characteristics.

Land use	io (cm min ⁻¹)	if (cm)	I (cm min ^{-1/2})	S (cm min ⁻¹)	A
OP	1.12	0.46	54.86	0.51	1.1
FL	0.55	0.21	26.02	0.17	0.75
CC	0.37	0.13	15.02	0.08	0.52
LSD (=0.05)	0.65	0.19	22.86	0.38	0.85

OP is oil palm plantation; FL is fallow land; CC is cultivated farm land;
 io is initial infiltration; if is final infiltration;
 I is cumulative infiltration; S is sorptivity; A is transmissivity

Table 1: SWAT Simulation Result.

Land use type	Area (04hm ²)	Precipitation infiltration (m ³)	Coefficient of Infiltration
Paddy field	22.52	157955280	0.21
Dry Land	20536	891673120	0.13
forest	23.18	232263600	0.3
meadow	562.5	469687500	0.25
shooby land	5.22	50560920	0.29
Residential land	16.25	86840000	0.16
Sandy land	25.06	61938296	0.074
Salinized land	79.46	188431444	0.071
Wetland	8.39	78463280	0.28
Total	441.69	2217813440	50.211

Table 1: Effect of Land use change.

Site	Land use	AWC (%)							
		0-15		15-30		0-15		15-30	
1	Pasture	16.01a	11.11b	7.02ab	1.012a	55.2a	53.1a	0.5010a	0.3900c
		10.72b	10.27b	0.604b	0.529b	48.7b	47.2b	0.4870b	0.3370d
2	Pasture	20.95a	16.53b	1.116b	1.576a	47.5a	45.1b	0.2190b	0.2480a
		14.71b	12.41b	1.031b	0.832b	46.6a	43.3c	0.1500c	0.0660d

Values with different letters (a-d) in the column indicate a significant difference (p<0.05).

Data Analysis:

A study of effect of land use on infiltration and porosity has attracted many researchers from the comprehensive disciplines including engineering, hydrology, environmental science agriculture and civil engineering. Notable studies have been presented on effect on infiltration. The review of finding from various studies is being carried out.

Effect on Infiltration: Yimer concluded slope position did not significantly affect infiltration capacity and soil moisture content and suggested that results can to a large extent be examined by differences in land use^[5]. Klaus attempted to create mirror images of soil water profiles, soil water functions and related properties during infiltration and given solution for water transport and retention in soil of different physical and chemical characteristics during this century^[14]. In the study by Ibeje assessment of effect of land use on infiltration shown the result of ANOVA concluded that the difference in infiltration rates between different land use were not significant at the 95% confidence level as assessed by non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis analysis of variance^[13]. Anderson is depicted near surface soil physical and chemical properties were co-related with infiltration related parameters, there was no correlation between overall infiltration rate and ASMC. Data indicated a strong positive Correlation between overall infiltration rate and SOM content ($P < 0.01$) and strong negative correlation between IR and Bulk Density in the top 10 cm ($P < 0.01$). Among all land use data the intercept parameter was uncorrelated with ASMC in the top 6cm ($P > 0.05$). Soil moisture content, silt concentration and extractable soil Cu content were uncorrelated with overall infiltration rate, slope and intercept parameter or estimated K_{sat} ^[11]. Biro study on effect on Soil Compaction and Infiltration Rate did an experiment with the woodland, the soil penetration resistance was 29% and 14.5 larger and infiltration rate was 60% and 45% smaller to the cultivated land and follow land respectively^[2]. Linares is depicted in table average statistic r^2 and s_x . And showed that Kostiakov model fitted best for the infiltration data and that there was statistical evidence that land use plays a key role on the infiltration process. Higher and more variable final infiltration rate were observed in native shrub forest land. The differential development of desiccation cracks among land use could have resulted in infiltration rate^[10].

Effect on Heavy Clayey Soil and Soil Infiltration Rate: Selim did an experiment to (Site1) Cultivated Field's infiltration rate at the beginning was low and decreased to reach the constant value. (Site2) Natural field was high and decreased to reach the constant value. (Site3) Fish Farm field was low and decreased to reach the constant value. The high initial infiltration for (Site2) NF was high due to low initial water content in the soil^[8]. Robertson presented a study of Human Impact on Ground Recharge and Nutrient Cycle the major cause of increasing NO_3 concentration in basin is modern mobilization. The basin groundwater has an isotopic component consistent with a soil N derived source and flushing of salt from sub root zone is evident in unsaturated zone samples^[16].

Effect on Infiltration Characteristics of Soil: Ogban carried out OP was similar to FL but significantly different from CC at $< \text{or} = 0.05$ level in their effect on initial infiltration rate. FL and CC were similar in Infiltration rate, OP was about 51% greater than in FL and about 67% than in CC. the final Infiltration rate was significantly higher by about 54 in OP than in FL, and about 72% than in CC. FL and CC were not significantly different at the 5% Level^[12].

Development of Quantitative Models for characterization: Bian carried out land use distribution by SWAT interactive interpreting method in **Table 5** shows that the highest coefficient of infiltration is the forest and wetland. Comparing the simulation result with the

tradition one SWAT model has advantages of time saving, result visualization and data acquiring, in the future it has more use in the regional water resources^[7].

Infiltration Capacity, Bulk Density and Soil Organic Carbon: Nord expressed as CV for all land use was generally high for the steady state infiltrability and the bulk density measurement and lowest for natural forests. CV for BD is low for all land use, which is an indication of low variation and precise measurements. Double ring infiltrometer is highly varying method, however very high number of SSI in this study made it possible to access the variation within land uses. Which suggests that variation is naturally large^[11].

Soil Organic Matter and Soil Physical Properties: Table 6 shows average value of soil properties for two land use and no significant difference in soil particle soil distribution were found between land use types. The MWD was lower on cultivated soil by 47.7 and 47.2% at 15-30 cm. Ks were significantly lower in dryland farming soil compared to pasture soil. There were significant difference AWC between dryland farming and pasture soil at a depth of 0.15cm^[4].

Relationship between Infiltration, Soil Moisture and Surface Runoff: Schiff carried out comparison of top soil silt loam can absorb a high rate of rainfall provided the initial soil moisture content is not too high. Good land use practices improves the conditions in top soil silt loam. After runoff begins infiltration rates drop even though gravitational water has not reached the sub soil and higher soil moisture content in of the upper portion of the topsoil. Pores seem to clog with water and containing variable amount of soil collides, greater the colloidal content greater the restriction^[9].

Automated Single Ring Infiltrometer: Most commonly used infiltrometers are single and double ring infiltrometers. Single ring infiltrometer involves driving a single metal ring partially in to the soil and filling it to the water **Figure 3: a)**. Double ring infiltrometer is contrast require two rings i.e. inner and outer, which creates one dimensional flow of water from the inner ring **Figure 3: b)**. Automated single ring infiltrometer can be easily fabricated and operated. It can be used for situations where a large number of readings need to be collected^[17]. **Figure 3: c)**.

Laboratory System set up to Infiltration Process: Renato investigated different aspects that the generator of artificial rainfall with uniform rain rate and result shown the significant accuracy of the conceptual model for local infiltration into horizontal soil surfaces and even though the quantitative evaluation of the effect of the slope on infiltration into bare soil^[15]. After reviewing various studies most of the eminent worked on the effect of land use on infiltration. This study would be stepping stone for hydrology practitioners.

Research Gaps, Status and Future Trends:

This study endeavors to bridge this gap. The innovative approach is that, whole data related to Soil Physical Characteristics is generated through field visit and lab analysis. A situation or state of infiltration is going to help increase water table. The study resents the applications of infiltrometer, Rainfall simulation and SWAT model data is self-generated. The review reveals that there is need of study to conserve water table.

Conclusion:

Land use effect on Soil infiltration is a process of many variables. The Field Survey, Laboratory analysis, Rainfall Simulation, Infiltration models, Statistical tests (ANOVA, Co-relation, and Regression etc.), Single/Double Ring Infiltrometer and Horton's, Philip's,

Kostiakov's and Philip's equations has been successfully used for Soil Infiltration process. From the above study, it can be said that rainfall Simulation, Single /Double ring infiltrometer, ANOVA, Co-relation, Regression and SWAT analysis is useful for studying effect of land use on soil Infiltration.

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